

EFFECT OF PARTICLE TYPE AND SHAPE ON THE STRENGTHENING OF NIAL MATRIX COMPOSITES*

J. Liu, K. Xu and R.J. Arsenault
Metallurgical Materials Laboratory
Dept. of Materials & Nuclear Engineering
University of Maryland, College Park, MD 20742-2115

ABSTRACT

The compressive yield stress of hot pressed NiAl composites containing Al_2O_3 and TiB_2 particles or whiskers was determined in the temperature range of 300 to 1400 K. Composites with 20 V% particulate were considerably stronger than the matrix at all temperatures investigated, and the TiB_2 additions resulted in a slightly stronger composite than either particulate or whisker Al_2O_3 at lower temperatures, but there was no significant difference in the strength of the composites with same size particle addition at higher temperatures. Particles of smaller sizes produced slightly stronger composites than the larger particles and even the whiskers. The strengthening due to the addition of TiB_2 and Al_2O_3 to NiAl can be accounted for in terms of an increase in the athermal yield stress and the thermally activated motion of jogged screw dislocations.

INTRODUCTION

The strengthening that occurs due to the addition of particles, of Al_2O_3 , AlN, TiB_2 to NiAl is not well understood [1-3]. The high temperature yield stress of composites has been analyzed in terms of a classical-continuum-composite-strengthening, i.e. a load transfer mechanism [4]. However, if this mechanism is applied to a composite containing spherical particulate additions, the load transfer is very small, a 5% increase in strength is predicted for a 20 V% composite. Experimentally it is observed that the addition of 20 V% TiB_2 particles to NiAl results in a factor of two increase in the yield stress at 1273 K [1].

If one attempts to perform a more rigorous load transfer analysis by the use of the Eshelby method, a problem exists. There is a restriction, which is presently placed, on the Eshelby method which requires that the matrix has to be treated as a newtonian fluid, i.e. the stress exponent (n) would have to be unity [5]. The observed stress exponents are much greater than unity, for example, in the range 6-11 [1].

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Another approach would be to consider the dislocation mechanisms that have been proposed to predict high temperature strengthening. However, very few detailed mechanisms have been proposed which take into account the presence of large second-phase particles [6,7]. From a consideration of dislocation climb over second-phase particles, it is possible to obtain a stress-strain rate relationship. The predicted stress is at least three orders of magnitude smaller than the yield stress of the matrix. There is another possible dislocation model which has been proposed by Blum and Reppich [7], however, if the calculated Orowan stress of the composite is low, the effect of the reinforcement on the yield stress is small. From a consideration of these mechanisms, it is apparent that the load transfer and the dislocation mechanisms cannot be used to explain the data.

Another possible contributing factor to this lack of understanding is the inconsistent data that has been published [2,8]. From this data it was speculated (as shown in Fig.1) that the observed strengthening was due in part to the particular type of addition [8]. However, it should be recognized that the different particle types have had different sizes and shapes [2,8].

Fig.1 A speculative yield stress vs temperature for the matrix and various composite. This speculation is based on some preliminary data [2,8].

An investigation was undertaken to determine if the increase in the yield stress of discontinuous TiB₂ or Al₂O₃/NiAl matrix composites was indeed dependent upon the type, shape, and size of the TiB₂ or Al₂O₃.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The composites that were produced for this investigation contained 20V% of Al_2O_3 or TiB_2 in a NiAl matrix. The NiAl and TiB_2 powder was purchased from CERAC Inc. of Milwaukee, WI, and the small Al_2O_3 particles were polishing grade Al_2O_3 , and larger Al_2O_3 was produced by grinding high-density-sinter Al_2O_3 . The Al_2O_3 whiskers were obtained from Du Pont, in Willington, DE. The Al_2O_3 , TiB_2 and NiAl powders were separated into various particle sizes by a sieving procedure.

A great deal of effort was devoted to develop an acceptable method of producing these composites. The present procedure for producing the composites is as follows:

- Dry blending of the reinforcement and matrix powders of approximately equal powder sizes.
- Hot vacuum uniaxial pressing (three different configurations were used).
 - Cylinders 25.4 mm in diameter by 37 mm in height at a pressure of 89 MPa and a temperature of 1673 K for 1 hr.
 - Cylinders 50 mm in diameter by 37 mm in height at a pressure of 55 MPa and a temperature of 1673 K for 1 hr.
 - Disks 100 mm in diameter by 6.35 mm in thickness at a pressure of 48 MPa and a temperature of 1723 K for 1 hr.

In the resulting hot pressed cylinders and disks the particles were randomly distributed in the matrix, and the density as determined by immersion tests was ~100%, but by metallographic examination there were some voids detected ~ 1-2 μm in diameter. The whiskers were oriented in planar array, perpendicular to the direction of hot pressing. The whiskers lie in plane which was parallel to compressive loading direction.

The cylinders and disks were sliced into strips ~ 6.35 mm in thickness and width by electrical discharge machining (EDM), then ground with a precision surface grinder into 4.76 mm square rods. The rods were then EDM into 6.35 mm lengths and finally the ends were surface ground so that the sample ends were flat and parallel to within $\pm 2.5 \times 10^{-3}$ mm. After the last grinding step the samples were annealed in a vacuum of 5×10^{-6} torr for 4 hours at 1623 K and cooled over a period of 4 hours.

The samples were tested in compression in an electric actuated testing machine in the temperature range of 300 to 1473 K and in a strain rate range of 10^{-6} to 10^{-2} s^{-1} . The tests were conducted in a vacuum of 5×10^{-6} torr and the samples were held at temperature for a sufficiently long period of time so that the test system could reach thermal equilibrium.

The initial portions of the stress strain curves for most of the tests did not have a well defined linear region. As a result, determining a 0.2% offset strain proved to be difficult. At the higher test temperatures it was found that an offset strain of 1.2% was in a portion of the stress-strain curve for which there was zero work hardening (Fig. 2). When using this offset strain (1.2%) there was less ambiguity in determining the yield stress.

The activation volume was determined by performing differential strain rate tests (Fig.2) and employing the following equation [9],

$$v^* = kT \left(\frac{\partial \ln \dot{\epsilon}}{\partial \tau} \right)_T$$

where k is Boltzmann's constant, T is absolute temperature, $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the strain rate and τ is the shear stress. It is assumed that the shear stress is one half of the compressive stress.

Fig.2 The stress vs strain of a 20 V% TiB₂/NiAl composites test at 1273 K and a base strain rate of 10^{-4} s^{-1} . There were two increase and decreases in strain rate undertaken during the test.

RESULTS

The addition of 20 V% TiB₂ or Al₂O₃ to NiAl results in a composite which is at least 50% stronger than the NiAl matrix (Fig.3 and 4) at all test temperatures. The data also indicates that the initial powder size of the matrix does not have any effect upon the yield stress of the matrix. The details of the subgrain or grain size of matrix and composites are presently being investigated, but the general trend is that subgrain or grain size of the matrix is much greater than that of the composites. Also, there is no particle breakage due to processing or during testing.

From the results shown in Fig.3, it is apparent that for a given size, the type of addition (TiB₂ or Al₂O₃) has a small effect on the yield stress of the composite, which is much smaller than speculated differences as shown in Fig.1. In the low temperature range (300 K), the yield stress of the TiB₂ is higher than that of the Al₂O₃/NiAl composite of the same particle size. The effect of the Al₂O₃ or TiB₂ on the yield stress at a higher temperature can be seen in greater detail in Fig.4. At this temperature, the yield stress of Al₂O₃ (5μm)/NiAl composite is slightly higher than TiB₂ (5μm)/NiAl composite.

The fact that the yield stress at 1273 K of the Al₂O₃ whisker composite, which have a large aspect ratio (length to diameter), produced a yield stress increase which is no larger than of 5 μm Al₂O₃ particulate is a very strong indication that a load transfer mechanism is not the mechanism of strengthening. This result also indicates that the shape of the reinforcement has no effect on the observed strengthening.

The activation volume (v^*) was determined from the differential strain rate tests and Fig.5 is a plot of v^* vs temperature for several of composites and the matrix. The data presented in Fig.5 can be divided into three temperature ranges 300-550 K, 550-850 K and 850-1373 K. In both the

high temperature and low temperature ranges there is very little difference between the ν^* of the composites and the matrix. In the intermediate temperature range there are differences in the ν^* , and there are data which indicates that in some cases the ν^* becomes infinite. This intermediate temperature range is the same temperature range where yield stress exhibits a small temperature dependence, and consequently the ν^* should be a large value approaching infinity [9].

Fig.3 Yield stress at a 1.2% off-set as a function of temperature for various type and sizes of reinforcements.

Fig.4 Yield stress at 1273 K and strain rate of $10^{-4} s^{-1}$ as function of particle size and type of reinforcement.

Fig.5. Activation volume vs temperature, for the matrix and several different composites.

DISCUSSION

As mentioned in the Introduction, the classical continuum theories and the dislocation climb mechanisms are not capable of accounting for the observed strength of Al_2O_3 or TiB_2/NiAl composites. However, the present data somewhat simplifies the situation, i.e. the observed strengthening does not depend to any significant extent upon the type of reinforcement.

There remains the fact that TiB_2 or $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiAl}$ composites have a higher yield stress than that of NiAl. There are several experimental observation which should be considered when developing a model or mechanism to explain the observed strengthening. From a previous transmission electron microscopy investigation [10], it was observed that there was a predominance of jogged screw dislocations, and that the subgrain size or shape did not change due to deformation at high temperatures. The v^* determined at high temperatures for both the matrix and composite are essentially the same values at the same temperature, and also at the same stress, which is a strong indication that the same rate controlling mechanism is operating in both the matrix and the composite.

If we consider Fig.3 and 5, it is possible to define an athermal yield stress, i.e. a yield stress which is temperature and strain rate independent. In the case of the matrix material, this would be in the temperature range of 450 to 800 K, as shown in Fig.3, the temperature dependence of the strength is zero or small, and the v^* is large in this temperature range. Another definition of the athermal stress is a long range internal stress.

A mechanism of strengthening was developed based on the following assumptions which are supported by experimental data:

- There is an athermal stress.
- The athermal stress does not decrease at high testing temperature due to temperature or stress.
- The TiB_2 and Al_2O_3 additions only increase the athermal stress.
- The thermally activated dislocation motion mechanism is the movement of vacancy

producing jogs in screw dislocations, and the parameters of this mechanism are the same in the matrix as in the composites.

It is possible to develop a computer simulation model which has the athermal stress as the only adjustable parameter. Figure 6a and b illustrate the agreement between the model prediction and the experimental results. The details of the computer simulation model are to be published elsewhere [11].

Fig.6a Plot of the experimentally determined yield stress vs temperature, also the predicted yield stress vs temperature for the matrix.

Fig.6b Plot of the experimentally determined yield stress vs temperature, also the predicted yield stress vs temperature for a Al_2O_3 (5 μm)/NiAl composite.

CONCLUSIONS

From data obtained in this investigation and the model considered, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The type of the reinforcement has a slight effect on the strength of NiAl matrix composites at lower temperatures (300 K), but no significant effect at higher temperatures (1273 K).
- Since whiskers and particulate Al_2O_3 have about the same strength, the shape of the reinforcement has no effect on the strength increase which is further proof that a load transfer mechanism is not applicable.
- The addition TiB_2 or Al_2O_3 to NiAl produces an increase in the athermal stress.
- The thermally activated dislocation motion mechanism is the motion of jogged screw dislocations.
- A model based on this mechanism, and the assumption that the TiB_2 and Al_2O_3 only increases the athermal stress produces a prediction which is in very good agreement with the experimental results.

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